

Two Wheel Self Balancing Robot for Telepresence Application

(Robot Pengimbang Diri Dua Roda Untuk Aplikasi Telehadir)

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the development of a Two Wheel Self Balancing Robot (TWSBR) for telepresence application. Conventional video conferencing tremendously fails to establish psychological and emotional connections between parties connected via this technology. Telepresence is an emerging technology that aims at addressing these gaps created by technology. It entails a “same room” or commonly called “across the table” experience. With a specific goal of stabilizing the robot in this project, Arduino Uno is being used to implement a Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) controller to stabilize the two-wheel robot. An Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) is being used to measure the tilt angle of the robot with the vertical axis (z-axis) as the reference point. The Arduino Uno microcontroller generates pulse width modulation (PWM) signals based on the error value of the tilt angle to stabilize the TWSBR. The gyroscope is difficult to calibrate physically as it measures the rate of the tilt angle, however, the accelerometer is can be physically calibrated as it measures the actual angle. The P control shows that a combination of PI, PD, and PID can stabilize the robot. However, PD control is highly not recommended for TWSBR. Whilst PI controls show some promising results, on the other hand, PID control proved to be reasonable. The three main objectives of this paper were achieved by successfully calibrating the gyroscope and the accelerometer, by redesigning the first generation TWSBR chassis with reduced height and specific component holders, and by stabilizing the robot with PID control at high oscillations.

Keywords: Two-wheel self-balancing robot, PID control, Telepresence

ABSTRAK

Kertas kajian ini telah menunjukkan perkembangan robot pengimbang diri dua roda (two-wheel self-balancing robot, TWSBR) untuk aplikasi telehadir. Persidangan video konvensional membawa keburukan seperti orang ramai tidak dapat menjalin hubungan psikologi dan emosi antara satu sama lain melaluinya. Jadi, telehadir yang memerlukan “ruang yang sama” ataupun pengalaman “di seberang meja” telah dikenalkan untuk mengatasi jurang tersebut. Demi tujuan menstabilkan robot dalam projek ini, Arduino UNO telah digunakan bersama dengan pengawal PID (Proportional Integral Derivative). Unit Pengukuran Inersia (Inertial Measurement Unit, IMU) telah digunakan untuk mengukur sudut kecondongan robot beroda dua tersebut dengan merujuk kepada paksi menegak (paksi-z). Mikropengawal Arduino UNO menghasilkan isyarat modulasi lebar denyut (Pulse Width Modulation, PWM) berdasarkan nilai ralat sudut kecondongan. Isyarat PWM tersebut ditambah dengan isyarat arah lalu dihantar oleh Arduino UNO kepada dua motor DC melalui pemandu motor supaya robot beroda dua tersebut dapat distabilkan. Seterusnya, giroskop sukar ditentu ukur (calibrate) secara fizikal kerana giroskop mengukur kadar sudut kecondongan manakala meter pecutan (accelerometer) dapat ditentu ukur oleh sebab meter pecutan mengukur sudut sebenar. Seterusnya, Pengawal P telah menunjukkan bahawa gabungan PI, PD dan PID dapat menstabilkan robot beroda dua tersebut tetapi pengawal P adalah sangat tidak digalakkan digunakan dalam TWSBR. Tambahan pula, pengawal PID adalah lebih digalakkan digunakan dalam TWSBR berbanding dengan pengawal PI walaupun pengawal PI juga dapat mengawal TWSBR kerana pengawal PID dapat menstabilkan TWSBR dengan masa yang lebih panjang. Akhir sekali, tiga objektif iaitu menentu ukur giroskop dan meter pecutan dengan mereka bentuk casis TWSR generasi pertama dengan mengurangkan ketinggian dan menggunakan pemegang komponen tertentu dan juga tidak dilupakan menstabilkan robot dengan menggunakan pengawal PID pada ayunan tinggi telah berjaya dicapainya.

Kata Kunci: robot pengimbang diri dua roda, PID, telehadir

INTRODUCTION

Technology aided communications have revolutionized the way people communicate. Video conferencing is common in the business world. However, it fails to establish psychological connections between parties connected by the technology which is what telepresence addresses. This project develops a TWSBR for telepresence applications. The focus is on stabilizing the two-wheeled robot

The first generation of this project had two main issues that are addressed in this project. The first generation TWSBR's chassis design was not optimum and the attempt to control the TWSBR was using the accelerometer only which is highly prone to microscopic noise just as it is to macro movements.

The TWSBR is a mobile inverted pendulum system which means it is a naturally unstable system. The idea of a mobile inverted pendulum was first proposed and successfully designed and tested by the Industrial Electronics Laboratory at the Swiss Federal Institute of Technology, Lausanne, Switzerland (Grasser et al. 2002). TWSBRs are modeled using Lagrange and Newtonian equations. They are commonly controlled using Linear-Quadrature Regulators (LQRs) (Bakarac et al. 2018) Banerjee et al. 2018) (Kafetzis & Moysis 2017) (Xin et al. 2011) (Wenxia & Wei 2017) (Peng et al. 2012), Fuzzy (Wardoyo et al. 2015), and PID (Wardoyo et al. 2015) (Bakarac et al. 2018) (Bhagat 2018) (Younis & Abdelati 2009) (Shaon et al. 2018) (Sugaya et al. 2017) (Shanmugavel 2018) (Iwendi et al. 2019) control.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Two Wheel Self Balancing Robots

Self-balancing robots have gained momentum over the last two decades. Inherently, a self-balancing robot is unstable in nature and would not be able to balance itself with the motors without any control mechanism in place. The idea of a mobile inverted pendulum was first proposed and successfully designed and tested by the Industrial Electronics Laboratory at the Swiss Federal Institute of Technology, Lausanne, Switzerland (Grasser et al. 2002). They used Digital Signal Processor (DSP) board to perform the equivalence of a microcontroller and a gyroscope with two incremental encoders mounted on each motor to measure the state variables. The measured state variables are then fed to a state-space controller to independently control the stability around the lateral

axis (pitch) and the vertical axis (yaw). However, the latest developments have been seen to use microcontrollers to implement the controllers (Shaon et al. 2018) (Younis & Abdelati 2009) (Shanmugavel 2018) (Bhagat 2018)

Modeling a TWSBR

The TWSBR can be modeled using Lagrange (Qian et al. 2017) (Xia et al. 2016) (Peng et al. 2012) (Iwendi et al. 2019) (Younis & Abdelati 2009) and Newtonian (Wenxia & Wei 2017) (Iwendi et al. 2019) equations. The Lagrange method revolves around the notion that energy is neither created nor destroyed. The Newtonian method revolves around Newton's laws of motion. Modeling a TWSBR is tedious as it requires profound details about the system. However, having a modeled system eases the controller design process.

Control algorithms

The implementation of a controller depends on the number of variables used to control the system as well as personal preference. TWSBR is a multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) system, however, it can be modeled as a single-input single-output (SISO) system. MIMO systems are usually controlled using Linear-quadratic regulator (LQR), H_{∞} Robust (Chen et al. 2018), State Space Controller (Grasser et al. 2002) (Sugaya et al. 2017) Fuzzy, and Model Predictive Control (MPC) (Bakarac et al. 2018). SISO systems are predominantly controlled using PID controller. MIMO system controllers warrant specific designs given the controlled system's specifications are available. On the other hand, PID control can be implemented without even having detailed information about the system. Such PID implementations use trial and error tuning methods to achieve the desired performance.

METHODOLOGY

The flow chart in Figure 1 shows the methodology of the project. It also shows the incremental steps in developing a TWSBR prototype. The success or failure of the projected is measured by how well the TWSBR can stabilize itself with a PID control implemented on the Arduino Uno Board.

Sensor Calibration

The project started with the calibration of sensors and actuators used. The sensors used are gyroscope

and accelerometer. On the other hand, the actuators used are two Direct Current (DC) motors. The two DC motors perform the equivalence of a cart of an inverted pendulum system. The gyroscope cannot be calibrated physically while the accelerometer is calibrated using a custom-designed calibration platform shown in Figure 4.

FIGURE 1: Project Methodology

Chassis Design and Development

The chassis was designed using OnShape – an online computer-aided design (CAD) program. The parts were designed separately, were 3D printed individually, and were later assembled. The components were allocated specific spaces on the chassis which means the component placement was considered during the chassis design phase. The assembling involved tight fittings, gluing, and bolt and nutting as well.

Electrical/Electronic and Mechanical Components Integration

The electrical and electronic components were integrated onto the chassis after assembling it. The components used are a LiPo battery pack, an Arduino Uno board with an L298P motor shield, an IMU6050 breakout board, and a buck converter. These components have pre-allocated spaces on the chassis as shown in Figure 2 that holds them tightly in place which makes it easier to mount and unmount the components

PID control Algorithm

Equation (1) is a PID control algorithm in the time domain. However, it is impossible to implement such an algorithm in a microcontroller as integrators and differentiators are tedious computation wise. Instead, estimations are necessary to implement such a high spec computational algorithm in a microcontroller. Equation (2) is the digital implementation of the time domain PID algorithm in equation 1.

$$PID = K_p + K_i \int_0^t e(\gamma) d\gamma + K_d \frac{de(t)}{dt} \quad (1)$$

$$PID = K_p * error + K_i * error * elapsedTim + K_d * \frac{(error - prevError)}{elapsedTime} \quad (2)$$

PD and PI control algorithms are derived by including the P and D components only for the former or P and the I components only for the latter.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Chassis Design

Figure 2 shows the improved chassis design. The components have specific spots on the chassis which makes mounting and unmounting easier. It helps with tuning and deploying the TWSBR without a component falling out of the chassis over time as it was the case with the first-generation model. The chassis is shorter; thus, it reduces the inertia of the chassis itself. The two DC motors do not require as much power as it was with the first-generation model due to its longer chassis height to stabilize the TWSBR.

TWSBR CHASSIS DESIGN

FIGURE 2: TWSBR Chassis Design

IMU calibration and combining accelerometer and gyro with a complementary filter

The gyroscope measures the rate of the tilt angle of the TWSSBR; thus, it involves time that cannot be physically quantified. This makes the gyroscope impossible to calibrate physically, however, there is a way to get even with the errors as shown in Figure 3. Less than 2000 raw gyroscope readings are taken and are averaged while the gyroscope is in the desired position. The subsequent gyroscope readings are subtracted with the averaged readings to eliminate the errors.

```

void setup() {
  // put your setup code here, to run once:

  Wire.begin();
  Serial.begin(9600);
  pinMode(13, OUTPUT);

  setup_mpu_6050_registers();

  digitalWrite(13, HIGH);

  for (int cal_int = 0; cal_int < 2000 ; cal_int++){
    read_mpu_6050_data();
    gyro_x_cal += gyro_x;
    gyro_y_cal += gyro_y;
    gyro_z_cal += gyro_z;
  }
  gyro_x_cal /= 2000;
  gyro_y_cal /= 2000;
  gyro_z_cal /= 2000;

  //Serial.begin(9600);
}
    
```

FIGURE 3: Gyroscope Calibration

The accelerometer measures the actual tilt angle; thus, it can be physically calibrated. The custom platform shown in Figure 4 is used to calibrate the accelerometer. Figure 5 is the actual platform used to calibrate the accelerometer. Figure 6 shows the desired pitch angle vs the actual pitch angles. There is a slight discrepancy at higher tilt angle values which can be ignored as the robot's reference tilt angle is zero degrees with respect to the z-axis.

FIGURE 4: Accelerometer Calibration Platform

FIGURE 5: Accelerometer Calibration Setup

FIGURE 6: Accelerometer Pitch Angle

DC Motor Calibration

It is important to calibrate the DC motors just as it is to calibrate the sensors. The two DC motors must turn synchronously. Figure 7 shows the encoder data which shows that motor B runs faster than motor A at PWM values lower than 150. This issue is being addressed using a trial and error method. A random integer value is added to PWM supplied to motor A and the corresponding speed increases are recorded until the speeds match the motor B's speed. The corresponding integer value is noted. It was noted that an integer value of three (3) did the magic. The results are presented in Figure 8.

FIGURE 7: Unsynchronized DC Motor Speed vs PWM

FIGURE 8: Synchronized Motor Speed vs PWM

TWSBR Stability - PID Control

PID is not the only controller that can be used for TWSBR stability. Several combinations of P I and D components were tried out as presented below. Figure 9 shows the block diagram of the TWSBR. The IMU6050 is used as a feedback parameter to compute the necessary error for stability control.

FIGURE 9: The Controlled System Block Diagram

P Control

The P control only involves the Proportional component of the PID control algorithm. Figure 10 shows the tilt angle error vs the number of readings. P control is not able to stabilize the TWSBR.

FIGURE 10: P Control

PD Control

PD control is highly flawed. It cannot be used to stabilize a TWSBR. Figure 11 shows the tilt angle error vs the number of readings of the PD controller. The TWSBR starts to oscillate right at the start. The frequency of oscillation is larger compared to the P control thus, this would not make a good control algorithm for a TWSBR.

PI Control

PI control involves the Proportional and Integral components of the PID controller. As shown in Figure 12, the robot remains in the equilibrium

FIGURE 11: PD Control

FIGURE 12: PI Control

position for a few seconds and then starts to oscillate just like the PD control, however, quite longer than the PD control. The TWSBR losses self-stability after an error reading of negative eighty (-80) degrees. The PI control gives an improved performance compared to the P and PD controls; however, it still succumbs to the oscillation

PID control

The TWSBR was proposed to be controlled by a PID controller. The PID control involves all the Proportional, Integral, and Derivative components of the control algorithm. In some instances, a system can be controlled by PD or PI controllers, however,

previous sections have shown that PI and PD controllers were unable to stabilize the TWSBR for a longer period. Figure 13 shows the tilt angle error vs the number of readings of the PID control algorithm. The TWSBR oscillated until it destabilized after a certain point.

FIGURE 13: PID Control

The sharp rise in the tilt angle error reading from negative to positive on the far right of Figure 13 is due to the robot trying to stabilize itself after toppling over.

The PID control gave an improved performance compared to the P, PI, and PD controllers, yet it succumbed to the oscillatory nature of the robot. The oscillation is due to the differences in the speed at which the motor is responding to the instructions from the Arduino Uno and the Arduino Uno's processing speed. The motor could not cope up with fast angle changes.

CONCLUSION

The mechanical design (Chassis) of the first-generation model warranted improvements as in the size of the chassis and the component placements on the chassis. The chassis designed for this project reduced the height of the chassis to reduce the inertia of the TWSBR due to its mass. The chassis was designed with specific spaces allocated to each component used in the project. The components are held firm to their positions making it easier to tune and deploy the TWSBR without having to look out for a component falling of the chassis which was the case with the first-generation model. The components can be easily mounted and unmounted.

The IMU6050 calibration was a major challenge at first as the interpretation of the gyroscope reading was obscure. The gyroscope does not measure the actual angle; thus, it is difficult to measure it against a known physical quantity. The accelerometer measures the actual angle; thus, it was successfully calibrated.

The self-stability is achieved when the tilt angle error of the TWSBR is zero.

The implementation of a P controller could not stabilize the TWSBR for a period longer than a second. The implementation of the PD controller is not so practical as the robot oscillates right at the start. The PI control showed some improvement compared to the P and PD controls. However, it could not remain in the equilibrium position after reaching an error value of negative eighty (-80) degrees. The implementation of the PID controller finally showed much better performance compared to the P, PI, and PD controls, however, it succumbed to the oscillation of the TWSBR

As discussed in the preceding sections, the control algorithm is not effective if the motor reaction time is not taken into consideration. The Arduino Uno processes data faster compared to how long it takes for the two DC motors to effectively respond to the commands from the microcontroller. It is important to fully understand how the two DC motors and the microcontroller communicate.

Replace the normal geared DC motors with stepper motors. A stepper motor has definite positional movements compared to a normal geared DC motors which are being used in this project. A clear establishment of a relationship between the working of stepper motors and the TWSBR tilt angle would stabilize the TWSBR since stepper motors have quantified rotational movements.

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